

zenodo

“A Study to Assess the Emotional Intelligence Among Nursing Students at Era’s College of Nursing, Lucknow”

Priya Mishra¹, Swarnlata Pandey², Laxmi Soni³, Neha Kasaudhan⁴, Pratima yadav⁵

Sandhya Awasthi⁶,

Prof. Priscilla Samson⁷ (Dean cum Principal, Era college of Nursing, Era University),

Mrs. Nazia Zaidi⁸ (Assistant Professor, Hind College of Nursing).

*Corresponding Author Email: naziiazaidi07@gmail.com

Date of Publication: 23/05/2026

Abstract: Emotional intelligence in the simplest word refers to the ability to recognize and regulate emotions in ourselves and others to make effective decisions. Emotional intelligence may be a relatively new term not more than years ago but the roots of the emotional intelligence can be found in the bhagwad geeta around 5000 years ago where krishnas sthithapragnya (most stable person) is very close to mayer and saloveys emotionally intelligent person and also the work of plato 2000 years ago where he stated “ All learning has an emotional base .Since then researchers scientist, educator , and philosophers have worked to prove or disapprove the importance of feelings and emotions in day to day life.

Objective : The study aimed to assess the emotional intelligence level among GNM 3rd year nursing students.

Material and Methods : In the present study, the non-experimental research approach with descriptive research design was used. 70 third year nursing students (GNM) were selected through the non probability convenience Sampling technique from Era College of nursing, Lucknow. Emotional intelligence assesses using Emotional Intelligence questionnaire and demographic details were obtained using baseline data.

Result: The findings of the present study shows the Mean emotional intelligence level which includes different domains (45% students have self-awareness, 21.25% students were having managing emotions, 42.5% students were having motivating behaviour, 41.25 students were having empathy and 51.25% students having social skill).

Conclusion: The study shows that each student had different kind of emotional intelligence level.

Keywords: *emotional intelligence, nursing students.*

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

The discovery of Emotional Intelligence has generated increasing interest during the past decade. Emotional Intelligence (EI) is defined by Salves and Mayer^[1] As “ the subset of social Intelligence that involves the ability to monitor one’s own and others feelings and emotions, to discriminate among them and to use this information to guide one’s thinking and action”. According to Goleman, this is an essential skill for the Emotional life, relationship, work and social activities of most if not all people^[2]. Competency in understanding one’s own and other ‘s Emotions consists of knowing the cause and consequences of different emotions as well as being able to differentiate between varying emotions. Good EI levels allow to harness emotions to guide cognitive activities and solve problems for example, by drawing on positive moods to enhance creative thoughts, managing one’s own and others’ emotions consists of elaborating emotions, healing situations and achieving individuals’ goals. The concept of Emotional strength was first introduced by Abraham Maslow in the 1950s.^[3]

The term “Emotional Intelligence” sees first to have appeared in a 1964 paper by Michael Baloch,^[4] and in the 1966 paper by B Leaner entitled Emotional Intelligence and emancipation which appeared in the psychotherapeutic journal: practice of child psychology and child psychiatry^[5]. Emotional Intelligence has been defined, by Peter Salovey and John Mayer, as “the ability to monitor one’s own other people’s emotions, to discriminate between different emotions and label them appropriately, and to use Emotional information to guide thinking and behavior”. In 1996, Goleman defined EI as “being able to motivate oneself and persist in the face of frustration; to control impulse and delay gratification; to regulate one’s moods and keep distress from swamping the ability to think; to empathize and to hope”^[6].

It is important to highlight the relevance of the power of Emotions and relationships in the work environment, and to study the deep impact of EI. Nursing is a profession strongly associated with individuals “ health and defined by some sorts of clinical Nursing care including interpersonal communication as well as other various activities, as a result of growing complexity of the health care environment, and increasing expectations of clients in today’s competitive Healthcare marketplaces.^[7] Nursing

zenodo

www.scientificjournal.in

YEAR: 2026

VOLUME: 4

ISSUE: 1

ISSN: 3107-4162

graduates must not only be competitive in technical and critical thinking skills, but also be equipped to manage "soft" people skills have been identified as Emotional Intelligence (EI) skills [8].

Some Researchers suggest that the nurses with higher EI display strong self-awareness and high levels of interpersonal skills; they are empathetic and adaptable; and they are more likely to connect easily with patients and meet their psychological needs. Thus, staff with these abilities can contribute to a higher-job performance [9].

Nursing students are required to manage numerous clinical situations, adopt to the different teaching styles and expectations of instructors, work independently towards objectives, and manage conflicts. In addition, some aspects of academic work may be considered highly stressful, such as taking exams and practicing nursing procedures in health care settings. These situations require high level of Emotional Intelligence [10].

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

"A study to assess the emotional intelligence among nursing students at Era's College of Nursing, Lucknow."

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

- To find out emotional intelligence among GNM nursing 3rd year students.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Moawad.S,Gemeay. M.E ,and Elsayers.A.H (2017) conducted a comparative study on

Emotional Intelligence among Nursing student. Data was collected from two settings

namely King Saud University and Tanta University. The study sample was 400 students and who are selected by convenience sampling. The tool was used in this present study. A socio- demographic and Academic Data Questionnaire and Emotional Intelligence scale .Thus ,it is seen that studies conducted come up with different results of the current study, it can be concluded that Emotional Intelligence and scores mother's education and family income ($p= 0.004$ and $p=0.034$ respectively) for Tanta students.[11]

Kannaiah .D, and Shanthi.R (2015) conducted a descriptive study , non-experimental

Research survey on Emotional Intelligence at work place Data was collected from five

University faculties- technical studies ,Natural science ,social science art and Humanities.The study sample was 512 students selected by Random sampling method. The tool was using in this present study was structured Questionnaire constructed by Goleman was used .The researchers from the study concluded the emotional intelligence was linked at every point of workplace performance and it was lofatmost importance now a days .Hence ,to be successful in life Emotional Intelligence plays a vital role.[12]

Ghorpade . M, dasila .p, gopalkishan .s (2020) conducted a descriptive non experimental survey design on the emotional intelligence among nursing students of selected nursing college in pune . Population on 30

students at nursing college and using the standard tool on emotional intelligence ,self structured clinical evaluation tool .the researcher from the study concludes that in this study only 6.6% of students had high level of emotional intelligence and 53.33% had low level of emotional intelligence which indicates that students need to develop their emotional intelligence.[13]

Stific.g, paynkihar.m,(2018) . Conducted a cross sectional description study design on the emotional intelligence among nursing students. The study included 113 nursing and 104 engineering student at the university in solveniashapiro wilks test of normally was used to test the sample distribution, while the differences in mean values were tested using students test of independent samples . Emotional intelligence was measured using the traits emotional intelligence questionnaire (tet questions) and schatle self report emotional intelligence test. The researchers conclude the study is emotional intelligence was higher in nursing than engineering student, slightly high in women than men .it was not associated with previous caring experience.[14]

METHOD

RESEARCH APPROACH

In this study quantitative research approach was used to assess emotional intelligence among nursing students.

RESEARCH DESIGN

The research design selected for the present study was Non-experimental descriptive research design.

RESEARCH VARIABLES

Research variables are qualities, attributes, properties or characteristics that are

Observed or measured in a natural setting without manipulating and establishing

Cause and effect relationships.

DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLES

In this study the demographic variables taken in to consideration are age , gender , Type of family , marital status.

RESEARCH SETTING

The present study was conducted at **Era college of Nursing.**

POPULATION

Target population-The target population was nursing students studying at Era college of nursing Lucknow

Accessible population -The accessible population was GNM Student who come under the age of 18 to 26 years and studying at Era college of nursing.

SAMPLE AND SAMPLE SIZE

Sample- The sample of the present study was GNM 3rd year student.

Sample Size- 70 ,G.N.M 3rd year students.

SAMPLE TECHNIQUE

Non-probability convenient sampling technique was used to select the sample for the study.

DESCRIPTION OF THE TOOL AND SCORING PROCEDURE

The tool consist of two sections:

Section-I: Demographic data

- Age
- Gender
- Type of Family
- Marital Status

Section-II :Emotional intelligence standard questionnaire

- Self Awareness
- Managing Emotion
- Motivating
- Empathy
- Social Skil

EVALUATION CRITERIA

Interpret your competency using the following criteria.

- 35-50 This area is a strength for you.
- 18-34 Giving attention to where you feel you are weakest will pay dividends.
- 10-17 Make this area a development priority.

Record your result for each of the emotional competencies: strength, needs attention or development priority.

Competencies	Strength	Needs attention	Development priority
Self awareness			
Managing emotions			
Motivating oneself			
Empathy			
Social Skill			

RESULTS

- Mean self awareness of the GNM 3rd year 55% students having need attention, 45% students having strength.
- Mean of managing emotion 21.25% students having strength and 78.75% need attention.
- Mean of motivating domains 42.5% student having strength 56.25% having need attention and 1.25% students having development priority
- Mean of empathy 41.25% students having strength 57.5% students having attention and 1.25% students having development priority.

- Mean of social skill 51.25% students having strength and 48.75% students having need attention.

ORGANIZATION OF THE DATA

SECTION-I

SOCIO DEMOGRAPHIC DATA

S.NO.	Variables	No. Of Frequency	Mean (%)
1.	Age:		
	18-20	06	60%
	21-23	03	30%
2.	Gender:		
	Male	00	00%
	Female	10	100%
3.	Family:		
	Joint	04	40%
	Nuclear	06	60%
4.	Marital Status:		
	Unmarried	09	90%
	Married	01	10%

SECTION-II

EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE STANDARD QUESTIONNAIRE

S. NO.	Domains	No. Of Frequency	Mean (%)
1.	Self Awareness		
	(35-50)	06	60%
	(18-34)	04	40%
2.	Managing Emotion		
	(35-50)	05	50%
	(18-34)	05	50%
3.	Motivating		
	(35-50)	05	50%
	(18-34)	05	50%
4.	Empathy		
	(35-50)	06	60%
	(18-34)	04	40%
5.	Social Skill		
	(35-50)	07	70%
	(18-34)	03	30%

zenodo

DISCUSSION

Objective: To assess the emotional intelligence among the GNM III-year nursing students

Emotional intelligence is a ability to monitor one's own and others emotions, to discriminate among them, and to use the information to guide ones thinking and actions (Salovey and Mayer,1990). We discuss (a) whether intelligence is an appropriate metaphor for the construct, and (b)the ability and mechanisms that may underlie emotional intelligence.

There were 70 samples included in the present study. This study result showed self-awareness 55% student is need attention and 45% student having strength, man aging emotion 78.75% student having need attention and 21.25% student having strength, motivating 56.25% student having need attention and 42.5% student having strength, empathy 57.5 % student having need attention and 41.25 % having strength, social skill 48.75 % student having need attention and 51.25 % student having strength.

REFERENCES

1. **Austin, E. J., Farrell, D., Black, C., and Moore, H. (2007).** Emotional intelligence, Machiavellianism and emotional manipulation: does EI have a dark side? *Pers. Individua. Dif.* 43, 179–189. Doi: 10.1016/j.paid.2006.11.019 4-I.A. Shaban et al. Undergraduate nursing students stress sources and coping behaviours during their initial period of clinical training: a Jordanian perspective *Nurse Educ. Proact.* (2012).
2. **Salovey, P.; Mayer, J.D. Emotional Intelligence.** *Imagination, cognition and personality.* Sage J.1990,9, 185-211.
3. **Goleman, Emotional Intelligence,** Bantam Books: New York, NY, USA 1995.
4. **Dhania, Priam (5 March 2021).** "Emotional Intelligence; History, Models and Measures. Research Gate.
5. **Baloch M (1964).** "Sensitivity to expression of emotional meaning in 3 Modes of communication. "In Deutz JR. et.al (eds). *The communication of emotional meaning* Mc Graw hill. pp. 31-42.
6. **Leaner B (1966)** "Emotional Intelligence and Emancipation". *Praxis Der kinder psychologic and neuropsychiatry* 15: 193-203.
7. **Goleman, D. Emotional Intelligence:** why it can matter more than IQ; Bloomsbury: London, UK, 1996.
8. **Bar-on R. Parker JDA.** *The handbook of emotional intelligence ce; Theory, Development, and Application at home, schools and in workplace.* San Francisco: Jossey – Bass Hardback; 2000.
9. **Goldenberg, I, Matheson, K, & Mantle, J. (2006).** the assessment of EI; A comparison of performance – based and self – report methodologies. *Journal of personality assessment,* 86.,33- 45.
10. **Caroche J.V., editor; Forges J. P., editor, & Mayer J. D, editor. (Eds) (2006).** *emotional Intelligence in everyday life* (2nd edition) New York: Beauvais psychology press.
11. **Joyce, R (2010)EI ;**An Essential Skill for nurses health network career .
12. **Winship.G,(2010) Is EI** an important concept for nursing practices ;*journal of psychiatric &Mental health nursing ,*17,940-948.
13. **Hopkins,M.M, Bilimoria,D.(2008).**Social and Emotional Competencies predicting success for male and female executives (1ed ., vol.27). *Journal of management development .*
14. **Carmeli,a. &Josman ,Z.E .(2006)** The rekalationship among emotional intelligence ,task performance , and organizational citizenship behaviors. *Human performance ,* 19 ,403-419 .